

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 – Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

FIELD RESEARCH

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Tools

Co-funded by
the European Union

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

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**ASAP Field Research
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Project Information

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Document Information

Result No.	R2.2.3_en
Result Title	ASAP Field Research Tools
Work Package	WP2 – Social Media, Preadolescents, and Meta-Cognition: ASAP Transdisciplinary Desk & Field Research
Activity	A2.2 – Field Research
WP Leader	DOBA Business School, Maribor
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Dissemination Level	PUBLIC
Short Description	Set of data collection protocols and survey instruments used for the ASAP Field Research with pre-adolescents, parents, teachers and school leaders. The tools were designed to explore the relationship between pre-adolescents, digital/social media, cyberbullying, and digital/media literacy through qualitative and quantitative methods.

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PROTOCOL FOR FOCUS GROUPS WITH PREADOLESCENTS

Date			
Start time			
End time			
Team members (researcher)			
Number of participants	M	F	Total
Name (or nickname) and age of participants	Name / nickname		Age

Introduction

My name is _____, and I work _____ (specify profession and place of work). Together with colleagues from Slovenia, Italy, Portugal, and the Czech Republic, we talk to preadolescents about the use of social media and their positive and negative sides. The research is part of the European project *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education*. In addition to talking to preadolescents to get a more detailed insight into the research subject, we will also talk to parents, teachers, and school principals.

Your participation in this conversation is voluntary. You can decide whether you want to participate, regardless of whether adults at school have asked you to participate. You can also choose to opt out of the conversation at any time. There are no right or wrong answers. We appreciate all your opinions, suggestions, and ideas. During the conversation, we guarantee protection and confidentiality. There will be no mention of your name or who said what in particular, we will only present the results collectively. The results of these discussions will be used to prepare educational materials for the project. Any information that could reveal your identity will not be included in the reports or presentations of the results.

We have prepared questions to ask you, which will guide us through the conversation. You can join in spontaneously during the conversation and answer the questions. We will record the conversation to make it easier to capture the essentials more easily. The conversation will last around 1,5 hours.

To be as faithful as possible to the messages you tell us, do you agree that we can record the conversation?

Do you want to continue the conversation now that you have all this information?

Introductory presentation

Each person says their name and something they like that starts with the same letter as their name (e.g., "I'm Sam and I like soccer").

How old are you, and what grade are you in?

With the aim of presenting, could you please search for an image online that best represents you and explain why.

Alternative (as tested in Italy)

Each person writes their name on a self-made table placeholder.

With the aim of presenting yourself, please find 3 words/images that you associate with the internet and tell the group giving motivation

Scenario 1 - Mean Online messages	
Imagine there's a student in your class named John. He has been excluded from a WhatsApp group of the class. John learns from a friend about the group and discovers that mean messages about his body/physical aspect have been circulating. John feels really upset and doesn't know what to do.	
Questions:	How do you think John might be feeling?
	What advice would you give John on how to handle this situation?
	What would you do if you were in his shoes?

Scenario 2 - Online "friend"	
Your friend Marion has made a new online friend while playing an online game - "Minecraft". They chat and play games together frequently. At some point the online friend wants to share more personal information and meet up in person.	
Questions	What should Marion do in this situation?
	What advice would you give her?
	How can she ensure her safety while still enjoying her online gaming and making friends online?
Note:	What does "personal information" mean to you?

1	In your opinion, what kind of problems it is possible to have in the online world? Would you like to share any situation/problem you had in the online world or heard about from a friend?
2	Who do you talk to about your problems? Are they the same people you talk/would talk with about your problems in the online world? <i>** (According to their answers ask questions about why they talk/don't talk with the different people - parents, teachers, adults, peers)</i>
3	Why do you decide to ignore something that happens in the online world or to talk about it to a person you trust? When can a person be trusted?

4	Do you feel you are understood by the adults in your life (parents, teachers, aunts, coaches, etc.)? Do you think they understand what you do in the online world and the difficulties you may have? Please explain your answers.
5	Do you talk with your parents about what happens in the online world? Do you feel comfortable (is it easy or is it difficult) talking to your parents about your experiences in the online world?
6	What tips (advice, instructions) have you received from your parents or guardians about the safe use of the Internet and social networks? And from your teachers and your school (e.g. school campaigns; expert talks...)? What does 'using the Internet safely' mean to you?
7	Have you ever talked to a teacher or school staff member about something that happened online? What was their reaction? Did you feel they helped you?
8	What kinds of topics or situations do you feel comfortable discussing with your teachers regarding your online experiences?
9	Do you have any tips for improving dialogue between kids, teachers and parents? How do you think parents and teachers could understand you better?

PROTOCOL FOR FOCUS GROUPS WITH PARENTS

Date			
Start time			
End time			
Team members (researchers)			
Number of participants	M	F	Total
Name (or nickname), number of children, age of children	Name / nickname	Number of children	Age of children

Introduction

My name is _____, and I work _____ (specify profession and place of work). Together with colleagues from Slovenia, Italy, Portugal, and the Czech Republic, we talk to parents about the use of social media among preadolescents and their positive and negative sides. The research is carried out as part of the European project *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education*. In addition to talking to parents to get a more detailed insight into the research subject, we will also talk to preadolescents, teachers, and school leaders.

Your participation in this conversation is voluntary. You can also decide to opt out of the conversation at any time. There are no right or wrong answers. We appreciate all your opinions, suggestions, and ideas. During the conversation, we guarantee protection and confidentiality. We will not highlight your name anywhere and who said what in particular, but we will present the results collectively. The results of these discussions will be used to prepare educational materials for the project. Any information that could reveal your identity will not be included in the reports or presentations of the results.

We have prepared questions we want to ask you, which will guide us through the conversation. You can join in spontaneously during the conversation and answer the questions. We will record the conversation so that we can more easily record what is crucial later. The conversation will last around 1,5 hours. Do you agree that we record the conversation so that we can convey the messages you will tell us as faithfully as possible?

Do you want to continue the conversation now that you have all this information?

Could you please introduce yourself, mentioning your name and something you like that starts with the same letter as your name (e.g., "I'm Greta and I like gardening")?

1. How old is your child, and what grade are they in?

Scenario 1 - Social Media: forbidden use	
Your child has been showing interest in TikTok. However, you haven't yet given your authorisation to install it on their smartphone, as they don't meet the minimum age to have an account on it. However, one day you take a look at your child's phone and you discover that he/she installed the app anyway and has been publishing content.	
Questions	How would you feel in this situation?
	How would you approach this situation?
	How can you ensure that you are protecting and at the same time empowering your child to be a responsible social media user?
Note:	What does "privacy" mean to you?

1	In your opinion, what kind of problems kids might encounter in the online world? Would you like to share any situation/problem your child had in the online world or you heard about it from a friend?
2	If your child were to face an online problem in the future, what do you think they would do? What factors might influence their decision to talk to someone about it or handle it on their own?
3	Who are the go-to people your child talks to when they encounter online issues? Why do they trust these individuals? What do you think fosters trust and dialogue between you and your kid?
4	Do you feel like you understand your child's online activities and the challenges they might encounter? Why or why not?
5	Do you feel you dedicate enough time and attention to talk and listen to your child? How does your kids know that you are listening to them?
6	What guidance or instructions have you provided to your child regarding safe internet and social media use including cyberbullying? Have you received any input or resources from their school or teachers on this topic?
7	How can the alliance/partnership between families and schools be strengthened in terms of addressing kids' online behaviours and activities in a common/consistent way?

PROTOCOL FOR FOCUS GROUPS WITH TEACHERS

Date			
Start time			
End time			
Team members (researchers)			
Number of participants	M	F	Total
First name (or nickname) and years of working experience	Name / nickname		Years of working experience

Important note for the focus group facilitator: in case you don't have enough time to go through all the questions, make sure to go through the Scenario and the questions written in Bold.

Introduction

My name is _____, and I work _____ (specify profession and place of work). Together with colleagues from Slovenia, Italy, Portugal, and the Czech Republic, we talk to teachers about the use of social media among preadolescents and their positive and negative sides. The research is carried out as part of the European project *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education*. In addition to talking to teachers to get a more detailed insight into the research subject, we will also talk to preadolescents, parents, and school leaders.

Your participation in this conversation is voluntary. You can also decide to opt out of the conversation at any time. There are no right or wrong answers. We appreciate all your opinions, suggestions, and ideas. During the conversation, we guarantee protection and confidentiality. We will not highlight your name anywhere and who said what in particular, but we will present the results collectively. The results of these discussions will be used to prepare educational materials for the project. Any information that could reveal your identity will not be included in the reports or presentations of the results.

We have prepared questions we want to ask you, which will guide us through the conversation. You can join in spontaneously during the conversation and answer the questions. We will record the conversation so that we can more easily record what is essential and crucial later. The conversation will last around 1,5 hours. Do you agree that we record the conversation so that we can convey the messages you will tell us as faithfully as possible?

Do you want to continue the conversation now that you have all this information?

Could you please introduce yourself, mentioning your name and something you like that starts with the same letter as your name (e.g., "I'm Greta and I like gardening").

1. What subject do you teach, and how long have you been an educator?

Scenario - Social Media: forbidden use	
You learn in one of your classes that there is a WhatsApp group created by your students where offensive messages are circulating. The messages are aimed at a particular student who is more isolated from the rest of the class and has some integration problems.	
Questions	
a	How would you approach this situation? How would you behave?
b	In which cases do you intervene directly with students? Do you involve other colleagues before taking action?
c	How do you make sure that your interventions have a real effect on your students' responsible behaviour as social media users?

1	What kind of problems do your students talk to you about? Do they talk to you about their problems online? Can you tell us some examples?
2	What kind of differences have you noticed in the behaviour of your students in comparison to 5 years ago? What has changed recently?
3	Have you ever had a student approach you to discuss something that happened online? How did you respond, and did it contribute to the student feeling better or finding a resolution?
4	Do you believe students feel comfortable discussing their online experiences with you? Why or why not?
5	Who do you believe are the go-to individuals that students talk to when they face online difficulties? What factors might influence their choice of confidants?
6	What would you expect your students to do if they witness someone being bullied or treated poorly online? How do you encourage positive bystander behaviour in online settings?
7	Do you have suggestions in order to improve trust and dialogue between kids and teachers?
8	Are there any specific resources or training opportunities you believe would be beneficial in helping teachers address online safety and behaviour effectively? Why do you find them useful? Please, explain.

PROTOCOL FOR SEMI-STRUCTURED SCENARIO-BASED INTERVIEW WITH SCHOOL LEADERS

Date	
Start time	
End time	
Team members (RESEARCHER)	
Gender of interviewee	M F
Years of working experience	

Introduction

My name is _____, and I work _____ (specify profession and place of work). Together with colleagues from Slovenia, Italy, Portugal, and the Czech Republic, we talk to school leaders about the use of social media among preadolescents and their positive and negative sides. The research is carried out as part of the European project *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education*. In addition to talking to school leaders to get a more detailed insight into the research subject, we will also talk to preadolescents, parents, and teachers.

Your participation in this conversation is voluntary. You can also decide to opt out of the conversation at any time. There are no right or wrong answers. We appreciate all your opinions, suggestions, and ideas. During the conversation, we guarantee protection and confidentiality. We will not highlight your name anywhere and who said what in particular, but we will present the results collectively. The results of these discussions will be used to prepare educational materials for the project. Any information that could reveal your identity will not be included in the reports or presentations of the results.

We have prepared questions we want to ask you, which will guide us through the conversation. You can join in spontaneously during the conversation and answer the questions. We will record the conversation so that we can more easily interpret what is crucial later. The conversation will last around 1 hour. Do you agree that we record the conversation so that we can convey the messages you will tell us as faithfully as possible?

Do you want to continue the conversation now that you have all this information?

Introductory presentation

Please introduce yourself briefly.

Indicate your first name or nickname.

State your vocation and years of service as a school leader.

1. How would you describe your school's current digital education policies and practices?
2. Are there any examples of successful digital education initiatives or practices in your school that you would like to highlight?
3. Do you want to raise any concerns or challenges related to digital education policies and practices?
4. Are there any specific areas or subjects where you feel digital education is lacking or could be improved?
5. Can you provide an overview of any past incidents or cases involving the misuse and/or abuse of social media within the school, including cyberbullying? How were these incidents initially identified and addressed by the school administration?
6. What specific measures or protocols are currently in place to prevent and respond to incidents related to social media misuse and/or abuse, including cyberbullying? Are there any anonymous reporting systems in place?
7. How did the affected students and their families receive support and guidance during and after these incidents? Are counselling services or resources available to help them cope with the emotional impact?
8. How do you involve parents and guardians in addressing and preventing incidents related to social media misuse and/or abuse, including cyberbullying? What resources or guidance do you provide to support parents in navigating these issues? How do you communicate with the parents/guardians in case of an incident?
9. How do you collaborate with teachers and staff to create a safe and supportive school environment, particularly in addressing cyberbullying incidents? What support or professional development opportunities are provided to them?
10. How do you involve students in developing strategies and initiatives to prevent cyberbullying and promote positive online interactions?
11. Have there been any changes or updates to the school's policies and procedures due to the past incidents of social media misuse/abuse, including cyberbullying? If yes, what were the main modifications made?
12. How are you updated on current trends and best practices in addressing cyberbullying? Are there any professional development opportunities for school staff in this area?
13. Do you believe that the school's current efforts to address cyberbullying are sufficient? If not, what areas require further improvement?
14. Is there anything else you would like to tell us?

Thank you for your participation!

PROTOCOL FOR ONLINE SURVEY FOR PREADOLESCENTS

We propose you to answer some questions to help us understand some aspects related to the use of the internet by boys and girls of your age in many countries in Europe. This is research we are doing as part of the *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education* (www.socialmediakids.eu), funded by the EU Erasmus+ Programme.

The questions you will find relate to your own thoughts and behaviour and therefore there are no right or wrong answers. We ask you to try to answer all the questions, taking as much time as you feel necessary.

Your name will never be linked to the answers you give; moreover, if you wish, you can stop completing the questionnaire at any time.

It may take you about 20-30 minutes to fill in the questionnaire. Click 'Next' to begin.

Thank you for your help, which is very valuable to us!

Q1. Class attended

- 5th grade
- 6th grade
- 7th grade
- 8th grade
- 9th grade

Q2. What would you say is your sex/gender?

- A boy
- A girl
- Prefer not to say

Q3. In what year were you born? Please write the answer in the box: _____

Q4. Do you have access to the internet?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

Q5. These days, how often do you use the following devices to go online?

	Never or hardly ever	At least every month	At least every week	Daily or almost daily	Prefer not to say
a) A smartphone	<input type="checkbox"/>				
b) A computer	<input type="checkbox"/>				
c) A tablet	<input type="checkbox"/>				
d) A games console	<input type="checkbox"/>				
e) A TV	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Show Q6 only if a device is used at least every month or more often (Q5). If answered “never or hardly ever” or “prefer not to say”, then go to Q12.

Q6. Do you have any of these devices JUST FOR YOUR OWN USE that you can go online with? Please tick one box on every line:

	Yes	No	Prefer not to say
a) A personal smartphone	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) A computer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) A tablet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) A games console	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
e) A TV	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Routing: for a smartphone YES (Q6a), go to Q8.

Q7. If you don't have a personal smartphone, are you allowed to use the smartphone of a family member (parents, siblings, uncles or other)?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Show Q8 only if Q6a is YES.

Q8. At what age did you get your first personal smartphone?

- below 10
- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13

Show Q9 only if Q6a is YES.

Q9. Before you had your own personal smartphone, did you have access to social media (e.g. using your parents', or siblings', or uncles' smartphone)?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Routing: for NO or PREFER NOT TO SAY (Q9), go to Q12.

Show Q10 only if Q9 is YES.

Q10. Was this time of “mediated” use useful for understanding how to behave on the social media?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Show Q11 only if Q10 is YES. Note: the question Q11 is not mandatory to answer.

Q11. Could you please explain how?

Q12. Imagine you are an adult and have children. At what age would you get them a personal smartphone?

- below 10

- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- from 16

Q13/Q14. How much time during the day do you spend on the internet? Please tick one box for weekdays and one for weekends:

a) During a regular weekday	b) During a regular weekend-day
<input type="checkbox"/> Little or no time	<input type="checkbox"/> Little or no time
<input type="checkbox"/> About half an hour	<input type="checkbox"/> About half an hour
<input type="checkbox"/> About 1 hour	<input type="checkbox"/> About 1 hour
<input type="checkbox"/> About 2 hours	<input type="checkbox"/> About 2 hours
<input type="checkbox"/> About 3 hours	<input type="checkbox"/> About 3 hours
<input type="checkbox"/> About 4 hours	<input type="checkbox"/> About 4 hours
<input type="checkbox"/> About 5 hours	<input type="checkbox"/> About 5 hours
<input type="checkbox"/> About 6 hours	<input type="checkbox"/> About 6 hours
<input type="checkbox"/> About 7 hours or more	<input type="checkbox"/> About 7 hours or more
<input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say	<input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say

Q15. Do you use any of the following social media? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- TikTok
- Instagram
- Snapchat
- Facebook
- YouTube
- Reddit
- Spotify
- WhatsApp
- Pinterest
- Twitter/X
- BeReal
- Twitch
- Discord
- Some other, name which one: _____
- I don't use social media
- Prefer not to say

Routing: for I DON'T USE SOCIAL MEDIA or PREFER NOT TO SAY, go to Q17.

Show elements of Q16 according to Q15 (only ask the details for social media that were "ticked").

Q16. On the social media you use, who opened your profile? Answer only for those networks that you have previously marked to use.

	Me	My parents	Me and my parents together	Someone else (specify who)
TikTok				
Instagram				
Snapchat				
Facebook				

YouTube				
Reddit				
Spotify				
WhatsApp				
Pinterest				
Twitter/X				
BeReal				
Twitch				
Discord				

Q17. In the PAST YEAR, has anything EVER happened online that bothered or upset you in some way (e.g., made you feel upset, uncomfortable, scared or that you shouldn't have seen it)?

- No
- Yes
- Prefer not to say

Routing: for NO and PREFER NOT TO SAY, go to Q23.

Q18. Can you please describe this situation with your own words – the last time it happened?

Q19. In the PAST YEAR, how often did this happen?

- Only once
- A few times
- At least every month
- At least every week
- Daily or almost daily
- Prefer not to say

Q20. The last time something happened online that bothered or upset you, did you talk to anyone of these people about it? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- My mother or father (or step/foster mother or father)
- My brother or sister (or step/foster/half sibling)
- My aunt/uncle
- A friend around my age
- A teacher
- School leader
- Psychologist
- School counsellor
- Police
- Someone else (add who):
- I didn't talk to anyone
- Prefer not to say

Q21. The last time you had problems with something or someone online that bothered or upset you in some way, did you do any of the following things? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- I ignored the problem or hoped the problem would go away by itself
- I tried to get the other person to leave me alone
- I tried to get back at the other person
- I stopped using the internet for a while
- I deleted all messages from the other person

- I changed my privacy/contact settings
- I blocked the person from contacting me
- I reported the problem online (e.g., clicked on a 'report abuse' button)
- Something else (specify): _____
- Prefer not to say

Q22. The last time this happened to you, did you have any of these feelings? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- Excitement
- Cheerfulness
- Curiosity
- Astonishment
- Embarrassment
- Shame
- Guiltiness
- Anger
- Humiliation
- Fear
- Anxiety
- Sadness
- Helplessness
- Disgust
- I felt nothing special
- Other, please specify: _____
- Prefer not to say

Q23. When you use the internet, how often does your parent/carer do any of these things? Please tick one box on every line:

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Encourages me to explore and learn things on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Suggests ways to use the internet safely	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) Sits with me while I'm using the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Talks with me about what to do if something online bothers or upsets me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
e) Explains why some online content can be dangerous for me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
f) Talks to me about the commercial activities I am exposed to online (for instance when someone tries to sell me something)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q24. Have you EVER done any of these things? Please tick one box on every line:

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Told my parent/carer about things that bother or upset me on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Helped my parent/carer to do something they found difficult on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

c) Argued with my parent/carer about what I do on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Asked for my parent's/carer's advice on how I should act online	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q25. Does your parent/carer allow you to do the following things on the internet and if so, do you respect the parent's/carer's decision? Please tick one box on every line:

	I'm allowed to do this anytime	I'm allowed to do this only with permission or supervision	I'm not allowed to do this	I'm not allowed to do this, but I do it in any case	Prefer not to say
a) Use a web or phone camera (e.g., for Skype or video chat)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Use a social networking site (e.g., TikTok, Snapchat, Instagram)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) Watch video clips (e.g., on YouTube)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Play games with other people online (e.g. Minecraft)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
e) Share photos, videos or music online with others	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q26. Does your parent/carer make use of any of the following...? Please tick one box on every line:

	No	Yes	I don't know	Prefer not to say
a) Parental controls or other means of blocking or filtering or keeping track of my activities on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Rules about how long or when I am allowed to go online	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) A service or contract that limits the time I spend on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Technology to track where I am (such as GPS)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Show elements of Q27 only if YES at Q26.

Q27. For all statements that you marked positive (with yes) in the previous question, mark whether you respect the stated rules and forms of control. Please tick one box on every line:

	No	Yes	Prefer not to say
a) Parental controls or other means of blocking or filtering or keeping track of my activities on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Rules about how long or when I am allowed to go online	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) A service or contract that limits the time I spend on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Technology to track where I am (such as GPS)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q28. When you use the internet, how often do you think your parent/carer checks on you afterwards? Choose one suitable answer.

- Never or hardly ever
- Sometimes
- Often or very often
- Prefer not to say

Show Q29 only if SOMETIMES or OFTEN/VERY OFTEN at Q28.

Q29. How do you know that your parents are checking on you after using the Internet? Choose one suitable answer.

- We have an agreement on that (e.g. to check once a day).
- They ask me for permission every time they want to check on me.
- I discovered it accidentally.
- Other (please specify): _____
- Prefer not to say

Show Q30 only if SOMETIMES or OFTEN/VERY OFTEN at Q28.

Q30. Why do you think your parent/carer do check on you? Write your answer in the box:

Q31. How do you feel about your parents checking on you after using the Internet? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- Ashamed
- Angry
- Humiliated
- Afraid
- Sad
- Astonished
- Helpless
- Protected
- Cared
- Important
- Embarrassed
- Disrespected
- Trust-worthless
- I felt nothing special
- Other, please specify: _____
- Prefer not to say

Q32. How much do you think your parent/carer knows about what you do on the internet?

- Nothing
- Just a little
- Quite a bit
- A lot
- Prefer not to say

Q33. Overall, would you like your parent/carer to take more or less interest in what you do on the internet?

- A lot less

- A little less
- Stay the same
- A little more
- A lot more
- Prefer not to say

Q34. According to the answer to the previous question, explain why:

--

Q35. How often...?

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) ...do you ignore what your parent/carer tells you about how and when you can use the internet?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) ...are your parents concerned in how much time you spend on social media/online?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) ...are your parents interested in what you do on social media /online?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q36. Have any teachers at your school done these things? Please tick one box on every line:

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Suggested ways to use the internet safely	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Encouraged me to explore and learn things on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) Made rules about what I can do on the internet at school	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Helped me when I found something difficult to do or find on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
e) Explained why some online content is good or bad	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
f) Helped me in the past when something has bothered me on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
g) In general, talked to me about what I would do if something on the internet ever bothered me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
h) Explained how to recognise disinformation online	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
i) Instructed me how to find reliable sources of information on the internet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for your participation!

PROTOCOL FOR ONLINE SURVEY FOR PARENTS OF PRE-ADOLESCENTS

Below is the questionnaire we use to investigate the use of social media and their positive and negative sides among parents of preadolescents. The research is part of the European project *ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education*.

Please, read each question and take your time to answer. All the questions in this questionnaire refer to your thoughts, behaviours and experiences, so there are no right or wrong answers. The data obtained will help us to better understand your experiences and needs, so we ask you to be completely honest when answering, and to answer all the questions. Filling in is completely anonymous (your identity will never be linked to the data obtained) and voluntary, and if you wish, you can give up filling in at any time.

When filling out the questionnaire, and in case you have more children, please fill out the questionnaire for a child aged 11-13. The expected time required to fill out the questionnaire is about half an hour. By clicking the "Next" button, you agree to participate in the research.

Thank you for your help and time!

Q1. What is the gender of the child for whom you are filling out the questionnaire?

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say

Q2. How old is the child for whom you are filling out the questionnaire? Please write the answer in the box:

Q3. What would you say is your sex/gender?

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say

Q4. In what year were you born? Please write the answer in the box:

Q5. What income group does your household belong to? Please choose only one answer:

- Below the average
- Around the average
- Above the average
- Prefer not to say

Q6. What is the highest level of education you have obtained? Please choose only one answer.

- Higher education or more (vocational degree, university degree, master of science or doctorate)

- High school education
- Elementary school or unfinished elementary school
- Prefer not to say

Q7. Do you have a paid job?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Q8. Do you have full access to the internet whenever you want to or need to?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

Q9. When you use the internet these days, how often do you use the following devices to go online?

	Never or hardly ever	At least every month	At least every week	Daily or almost daily	Prefer not to say
a) A smartphone	o	o	o	o	o
b) A desktop computer, laptop or notebook computer	o	o	o	o	o
c) A tablet	o	o	o	o	o
d) A games console	o	o	o	o	o
e) A TV	o	o	o	o	o

Q10./Q11. How much time during the day do you spend on the internet? Please tick one box for weekdays and one for weekends:

a) During a regular weekday:

- Little or no time
- About half an hour
- About 1 hour
- About 2 hours
- About 3 hours
- About 4 hours
- About 5 hours
- About 6 hours
- About 7 hours or more
- Prefer not to say

b) During a regular weekend-day:

- Little or no time
- About half an hour
- About 1 hour
- About 2 hours
- About 3 hours
- About 4 hours
- About 5 hours
- About 6 hours
- About 7 hours or more
- Prefer not to say

Q12. Do you use any of the following social media? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- TikTok
- Instagram
- Snapchat
- Facebook
- YouTube

- Reddit
- Spotify
- WhatsApp
- Pinterest
- Twitter/X
- BeReal
- Twitch
- Discord
- Some other, name which one: _____
- I don't use social media
- Prefer not to say

Q13. Does your child have any of these devices JUST FOR HIS/HER OWN USE that he/she can go online with? Please tick one box on every line:

	Yes	No	Prefer not to say
a) A personal smartphone	o	o	o
b) A desktop computer, laptop or notebook computer	o	o	o
c) A tablet	o	o	o
d) A games console	o	o	o
e) A TV	o	o	o

Routing: if Q13a is NO or PREFER NOT TO SAY, go to Q16.

Q14. At what age did you decide to give your child a smartphone? Please write the answer in the box:

Q15. What was the reason you decided to give your child a smartphone?

Q16. Does your child use any of the following social media? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- TikTok
- Instagram
- Snapchat
- Facebook
- YouTube
- Reddit
- Spotify
- WhatsApp
- Pinterest
- Twitter/X
- BeReal
- Twitch
- Discord
- Some other, name which one: _____

- He/she doesn't use social media
- Prefer not to say

Routing: if Q16 is *DOESN'T USE SOCIAL MEDIA* or *PREFER NOT TO SAY*, go to Q18.

Show elements of Q17 according to Q16 (only ask the details for social media that were "ticked").

Q17. On the social media your child uses, who opened his/her profile? Answer only for those networks that you have previously marked your child uses.

	Me as a parent	Child independently	Me and my child together	Someone else (specify who)
TikTok				
Instagram				
Snapchat				
Facebook				
YouTube				
Reddit				
Spotify				
WhatsApp				
Pinterest				
Twitter/X				
BeReal				
Twitch				
Discord				

Q18. How often you do any of these things? Please tick one box on every line:

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Encourage your child to explore and learn things on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Suggest your child ways to use the internet safely	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) Sit with your child while he/she is using the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Talk to your child about what to do if something online bothers or upsets him/her	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) Explain why some online content can be dangerous for him/her	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) Talk to your child about the commercial activities he/she is exposed to online (for instance when someone tries to sell him/her something)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q19. Has your child ever...

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Told you about things that bother or upset him/her on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Helped you do something you found difficult on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) Argued with you about what he/she does on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Asked for advice on how he/she should act online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q20. For each of these actions, please indicate if you CURRENTLY let your child perform them whenever she/he wants, or let her/him perform them but only with your permission or supervision, or you never let her/him perform them.

	Can do this anytime	Can only do this with permission or supervision	Can never do this	Prefer not to say
a) Use a web or phone camera (e.g., for Skype or video chat)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Use a social networking site (e.g., TikTok, Snapchat, Instagram,)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) Watch video clips (e.g., on YouTube)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Play games with other people online (e.g. Minecraft)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) Share photos, videos or music online with others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q21. Do you make use of any of the following...?

	No	Yes	Prefer not to say
a) Parental controls or other means of blocking or filtering or keeping track of your child's activities on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Rules about how long or when your child is allowed to go online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) A service or contract that limits the time your child spends on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Technology to track where your child is (such as GPS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q22. When your child uses the internet, how often do you check the following things afterwards?

	Never or hardly ever	Some-times	Often or very often	Prefer not to say

a) Which friends or contacts he/she added to his/her social networking profile	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) The messages in his/her email or an app for communicating with people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) His/her profile on a social networking site or online group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Which online content he/she viewed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) The apps he/she downloaded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) The in-app purchases he/she made	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Routing: if NEVER OR HARDLY EVER at all the items of Q22, then go to Q24.

Q23. What kind of arrangement did you make with your child with respect to you checking on him/her after using the Internet? Select one answer.

- We agreed on that (e.g. to check once a day).
- I ask my child for permission every time I want to check on him/her.
- We have no agreement on that but I do it anyway and my child does not know about it.
- We have no agreement on that but I do it anyway and my child knows about it.
- Other (please specify): _____
- Prefer not to say.

Q24. How much do you think you know about what your child does on the Internet?

- Nothing
- Just a little
- Quite a bit
- A lot
- Prefer not to say

Q25. As far as you are aware, in the past year, has something happened online that has bothered or upset your child (e.g. made them feel uncomfortable, upset, or feel that they shouldn't have seen it)?

- No
- Yes
- Prefer not to say

Routing: if NO or PREFER NOT TO SAY at Q25, go to Q29.

Show Q26 only if Q25 is YES.

Q26. Can you please describe this situation with your own words the last time it happened?

Q27. As far as you are aware of, how often did this happen in the PAST YEAR?

- Only once

- A few times
- At least every month
- At least every week
- Daily or almost daily
- Prefer not to say

Q28. Think about the last time your child told you about things that bothered or upset him/her on the Internet. How did you react and support your child in this case? Thick all the options that apply.

- Engage in open and non-judgmental communication to understand the child's experience.
- Report the incident to the school or appropriate authorities (e.g. law enforcement).
- Limit or monitor the child's online activities for a certain period.
- Seek guidance from educational resources on internet safety for children.
- Encourage the child to talk to a trusted adult, such as a teacher or counsellor.
- Collaborate with other parents to address the issue collectively.
- Attend parenting workshops or seminars on online safety.
- Utilize parental control tools or apps to enhance online monitoring.
- Encourage the child to take breaks from digital devices and engage in offline activities.
- Consult with professionals, such as child psychologists.
- Foster a supportive environment at home to help the child cope emotionally.
- Teach the child strategies for dealing with online conflicts and challenges.
- Contact the platform or service where the issue occurred to report and seek resolution.
- I suggested the kid to ignore the situation/the problem.
- Other (please specify): _____

Q29. To what extent, if at all, do you feel you can help your child to cope with anything online that bothers or upsets them?

- Not at all
- Not very much
- A fair amount
- A lot
- Don't know

Q30. How often...?

	Never or hardly ever	Some-times	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) ...does your child ignore what you tell him/her about how and when he/she can use the internet?	o	o	o	o
b) ...are you concerned in how much time your child spends on social media/online?	o	o	o	o
c) ...are you interested in what your child does on social media /online?	o	o	o	o

Q31. In general, where do you get information and advice on how to help and support your child on the internet and keep him or her safe? Thick all the options that apply.

- Parenting workshops or seminars organized by schools or community organizations.

- Online articles and blogs dedicated to parenting and online safety.
- Educational websites and resources specifically focused on internet safety for children.
- Social media groups or forums for parents discussing online safety.
- Books and publications on parenting.
- Parent-teacher association (PTA) meetings or resources.
- Government or non-profit organizations' materials on internet safety.
- Webinars and online courses on online safety.
- Information provided by the child's school or educational institution.
- Parenting apps or tools with features related to online safety.
- Consultation with school counsellors or support staff.
- Professional counselling services.
- Local community events or workshops addressing online safety.
- Recommendations from other parents within their social network.
- Other (please specify): _____

Q32. Where would you like to get that kind of information or advice from in the future?

- Your child's school
- Television
- Radio
- Newspapers or magazines
- Government
- Local authorities
- Children's welfare organisations/charities
- Websites
- Family or friends
- From my child
- Other sources (please add):

Q33. Would it be useful for you if your child's school provided an open space for discussion about parenting issues, including internet safety?

- Not at all
- Not very much
- A fair amount
- A lot
- Don't know

Thank you for your participation!

PROTOCOL FOR ONLINE SURVEY FOR TEACHERS OF PREADOLESCENTS

Below is the questionnaire we use to investigate the use of social media and their positive and negative sides among preadolescents. The research is part of the European project *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education*.

Please read each question and take your time to answer. All the questions in this questionnaire refer to your thoughts, behaviours and experiences, so there are no right or wrong answers. The data obtained will help us to better understand the experiences and needs of the students (as well as the needs of teachers), so we ask you to be completely honest when answering, and to answer all the questions. Filling in is completely anonymous (your identity will never be linked to the data obtained) and voluntary, and if you wish, you can give up filling in at any time.

When filling out the questionnaire, and in case you teach children of various age, please, have in mind the preadolescents aged 11-13. The expected time required to fill out the questionnaire is about half an hour. By clicking the "Next" button, you agree to participate in the research.

Thank you for your help and time!

Q1. What would you say is your sex/gender?

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say

Q2. In what year were you born? Please write the answer in the box: _____

Q3. How many years of experience do you have with teaching? Put down the number of years you have been teaching. _____

Q4. Are you in a position of a class-director in this school year?

- YES
- NO

Q5. Do you have kids yourself?

- YES
- NO

Routing: if NO at Q5, go to Q7.

Q6. Add information about gender and age of each child.

--

Q7. Do you have full access to the internet whenever you want to or need to?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

Q8 When you use the internet these days, how often do you use the following devices to go online?

	Never or hardly ever	At least every month	At least every week	Daily or almost daily	Prefer not to say
a) A smartphone	o	o	o	o	o
b) A desktop computer, laptop or notebook computer	o	o	o	o	o
c) A tablet	o	o	o	o	o
d) A games console	o	o	o	o	o
e) A TV	o	o	o	o	o

Q9/Q10 How much time during the day do you spend on the internet? Please tick one box for weekdays and one for weekends:

a) During a regular weekday:

- Little or no time
- About half an hour
- About 1 hour
- About 2 hours
- About 3 hours
- About 4 hours
- About 5 hours
- About 6 hours
- About 7 hours or more
- Prefer not to say

b) During a regular weekend-day:

- Little or no time
- About half an hour
- About 1 hour
- About 2 hours
- About 3 hours
- About 4 hours
- About 5 hours
- About 6 hours
- About 7 hours or more
- Prefer not to say

Q11. Do you use any of the following social media? Please tick as many boxes as needed:

- TikTok
- Instagram
- Snapchat
- Facebook
- YouTube
- Reddit
- Spotify
- WhatsApp
- Pinterest
- Twitter/X
- BeReal
- Twitch
- Discord
- Some other, please name which one: _____
- I don't use social media
- Prefer not to say

Q12. Think of the time you spend with the students at your school aged 11-13 in the past year (both during school hours or otherwise). How often have you done any of these things? Please, tick one box on every line:

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Encouraged your students to explore and learn things on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Suggested your students ways to use the internet safely	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) In general, talked to your students about what they would do if something online ever bothered them	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Helped your students when they found something difficult to do or find on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) Explained why some online content is good or bad	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) Helped your students in the past when something has bothered them on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
g) Made rules about what the students can do on the internet at school	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
h) Explained how to recognise disinformation online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
i) Instructed your students how to find reliable sources of information on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q13. In the past year, did the students at your school aged 11-13...

	Never or hardly ever	Sometimes	Often or very often	Prefer not to say
a) Tell you about things that bother or upset them on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) Help you do something you found difficult on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) Start a discussion with you about what they do on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) Ask for advice on how they should act online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) Ask about something that they have seen advertised online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) Ask for help with a situation on the internet that they could not handle	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

ROUTING: if NEVER OR HARDLY EVER or PREFER NOT TO SAY at Q13a, go to Q16. Show Q14, if Q13a is SOMETIMES or OFTEN OR VERY OFTEN.

Q14. According to your answer to the previous question, students sometimes or often/very often told you about things that bothered or upset them in the past year. Can you please describe this situation with your own words - the last time it happened?

Show Q15, if Q13a is SOMETIMES or OFTEN OR VERY OFTEN.

Q15. Think about the last time your students aged 11-13 told you about things that bothered or upset them on the Internet. How did you react and support your student(s) in this case? Tick all the options that apply.

- Provided emotional support and a safe space for the child to talk about their experiences.
- Reported the incident to the school administration for further action.
- Contacted the child's parents or guardians to discuss the situation.
- Offered guidance on responsible internet and social media use.
- Educated the entire class about online safety and responsible online behaviour.
- Collaborated with school counsellors to provide additional support.
- Engaged in conflict resolution and mediated between students involved.
- Referred the child to external support resources or organizations.
- Monitored and supervised the child's online activities during school hours.
- Document the incident and keep a record for future reference or reporting.
- Other, please specify: _____
- Prefer not to answer

Q16. In general, do you believe your students aged 11-13 feel comfortable discussing their online experiences with you?

- Totally uncomfortable
- Quite uncomfortable
- Quite comfortable
- Totally comfortable
- Prefer not to answer

ROUTING: if Q16 is "prefer not to answer", go to Q18.

Q17. Explain your answer to the previous question with your own words (why do you think students either feel uncomfortable or comfortable discussing their online experiences with you?)

Q18. To what extent, if at all, do you feel you can help your students aged 11-13 to cope with anything online that bothers or upsets them?

- Not at all
- Not very much
- A fair amount

- A lot
- Don't know

Q19. In general, where do you get information and advice on how to help and support your students aged 11-13 on the internet and keep them safe? Tick all the options that apply.

- Professional development workshops or training sessions provided by the school.
- Educational conferences or seminars on online safety.
- School district or educational authority resources.
- Teacher forums and online communities.
- Guidance from school counsellors or support staff.
- Educational websites and online resources.
- Books and publications on internet safety for preadolescents.
- Colleague collaboration and sharing of best practices.
- Webinars and online courses focused on online safety.
- Government or non-profit organizations' materials
- School or district policies and guidelines.
- Other (please specify).

Q20. Where would you like to get that kind of information or advice from in the future? Tick all the options that apply.

- Professional development workshops or training sessions provided by the school.
- Educational conferences or seminars on online safety.
- School district or educational authority resources.
- Teacher forums and online communities.
- Guidance from school counsellors or support staff.
- Educational websites and online resources.
- Books and publications on internet safety for preadolescents.
- Colleague collaboration and sharing of best practices.
- Webinars and online courses focused on online safety.
- Government or non-profit organizations' materials
- School or district policies and guidelines.
- Other (please specify).

Q21. Do you believe the following topics are well-covered in the school curriculum?

	YES	NO	Prefer not to say
a) Online safety	o	o	o
b) Online risks/threats	o	o	o
c) Digital literacy	o	o	o

Q22. Are any of the topics related to online safety, online risk/threats, digital literacy covered in the curriculum of the course(s) that you are teaching?

- YES
- NO
- Prefer not to say

Q23. How would you assess your school's endeavours to contribute to online safety and to promote safe/responsible behaviours on the Internet among the students aged 11-13?

- Insufficient
- Satisfactory
- Excellent
- Prefer not to say

Show Q24, if Q23 is "insufficient" or "satisfactory".

Q24. In the previous question, you assessed your school's endeavours to contribute to online safety as insufficient or satisfactory. In your opinion, what should be improved at your school?

Thank you for your participation!

FIELD RESEARCH

Set of data collection protocols and survey instruments used for the ASAP Field Research with pre-adolescents, parents, teachers and school leaders. The tools were designed to explore the relationship between pre-adolescents, digital/social media, cyberbullying, and digital/media literacy through qualitative and quantitative methods.

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